

**THE PLACE OF ARABIC LITERATURE IN MANAGING INSECURITY
WITHIN NIGERIA'S IMMEDIATE NEIGHBOURHOOD****SURAKAT Rafiu Olaniyi, Ph.D**

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Abstract

The basic responsibility of the government is the provision of security and welfare of the people. The rising waves of insecurity in Nigeria have caused disorderliness, anarchy, chaos, violence, conflict, hardships, retrogression and unsafe situation within Nigerian neighbourhood. Proving to be a serious issue threatening the social well-being of the people, this paper uses theoretical approach to explore the evils of insecurity in Nigeria with a view to employing the moral lessons derivable from Arabic literature to educate the younger ones to refrain from engaging in violence and other related offences. However, the study recommends that government should take a proactive step in creating job opportunities for all Nigerian youths so that they may not be unnecessarily engaged by the miscreants to perpetrate evils. Therefore, the ruling authority should imbibe good governance by displaying the principle of fundamental human right. Arabic literature should be encouraged to be studied as a compulsory subject/course right from the secondary school levels up to the higher institutions so that its moral lesson could be perfectly acquired and utilised. Also, the living standard of all Nigerians should be the concern of all the stakeholders in the nation building in order to be in a safe, favourable and enjoyable environment.

Keywords: Arabic Literature, Insecurity, Managing, Nigeria, Neighbourhood, Place.

Introduction

In this contemporary world, safety of life and property is the purpose of human creation, according to the Qur'an. The two must remain sacred for the stability and peace to reign for the survival of human race. Every nation should therefore struggle to prepare adequately for the citizens to live in free and secure environment for protecting their national interest, identity and sovereignty. The word insecurity is known in Arabic language as Mutaqalqal (مُتَقَلِّقٌ) meaning unsafe environment. Insecurity is a critical issue that has jeopardized the sustainability of Nigeria as a nation perceived to be the giant of Africa. In the real sense, the security of life and property is supposed to remain sacred for the

socio-economic survival and sustainable development of a nation such as Nigeria. The rising wave of insecurity in the Nigerian society has been on the increase to the extent that a day is not spared without hearing people perpetrating the acts of insecurity. This menace has symbolized unprotected place of abode for the innocent citizens of the state, because the insecurity has indirectly destabilised the existing socio-cultural tranquillity and sustainable development. Correspondingly, the insecurity has led the nation to be wallowing in great difficulties affecting human development, via promotion of the general well-being of the people residing in the state.

Therefore, insecurity negates living in a situation that admits settling in a very conducive environment for the protection of individuals and their belongings from the hostile. The hostility or the evil of insecurity discourages many people from travelling around or within a given natural space or elsewhere without threats to their lives. The fear of insecurity has subjected many people not to sleep with their two eyes firmly closed. Achumba (2013) opines that insecurity is interpreted in many ways. Some people consider it to mean lack of safety or the existence of danger, some view it as hazard or uncertainty while other category of people perceive it as lack of stability or protection. Tella. (2015) as well as Adeola and Oluyemi (2012) hint that insecurity poses some difficulty for individuals within a state to participate or get involved in sustainable activities that can push the state forward. However, the fundamental causes of insecurity are traceable to many factors such as child neglect, unemployment, inequality, bad governance, poor leadership, among others, (Surakat, 2014).

According to the submission of Emmanuel and Emily (2019), insecurity makes everything difficult for individuals within a state to have a very meagre input in the economic and social development of a state without adequate security. From the look of things, the principle behind societal sustainability is factually meaningless in the absence security. So, under the conditions of peace and security, the nation and its populace can live happily and direct their efforts and resources towards improving human life. Emphatically, insecurity undermines the dreams and aspiration of the great dynamites owing to its obvious negative consequences and unexplainable challenges nation-wide. In managing insecurity across the state, environmental protection should be the concerns of all and sundry to ensure a secured place for both humans and non-humans. By doing this, effort to live a safe and healthy life is achievable.

The main objective of this paper is to affirm that Arabic literature is capable of managing the menace of insecurity in Nigeria, because Arabic literature teaches moral, patience, perseverance, social and cultural

values, so that Nigerian society can be worthy of living harmoniously.

Concept of Insecurity

Security is an enigmatic concept that is interpreted by various scholars to mean different things according to the time and the usage in human history. United Nations (1994) sees security as protection from hidden and hurtful disruption in the daily activities, at home, offices, communities, etc. This implies that security borders much on ensuring safety of lives and properties.

Williams (2008) views security from the socio-political perspectives that it involves the ability to pursue cherished political and social ambitions peacefully. That is to say that security is socio-political in nature as without security there can be no political stability, and at the same time, social activities will be in a complete dilemma. Some people interpret security as safety to the average man or woman, some see it as protection from harm and risk, while others consider it as an assured physical safety/protection (Adagba, 2012).

However: research reveals that the word insecurity connotes different interpretations. It signifies danger; hazard; uncertainty; lack of protection; and lack of safety. Insecurity, according to Baldwin (1997), is the state of being subject in every respect to terror, threat, risk, molestation, bullying, harassment, etc. According to him, insecurity can be conceived as a threat to the state often accounted for the arms and nuclear weapon to protect the state.

In the summation of Nasiru (2023), insecurity is being used in a number of ways. Many people take it to mean lack of safety, or the existence of danger, hazard, disturbed, lack of protection and safety. Achumba, Ighomeroho and Akpor (2013) define insecurity from two perspectives. First, insecurity is the state of being open or subject to danger, threat of danger, where danger is the condition of being susceptible to harm or being exposed to risk or anxiety, where anxiety is a vague unpleasant emotion that is experienced in anticipation of some misfortunes. In the submission of Beland (2005), insecurity is the state of fear or anxiety stemming from a concrete or alleged lack of protections. The scholar refers to insecurity as lack of or inadequate freedom from danger. The implication is that insecurity

is an absence of peace, harmony, orderliness and security. Nwanegbo and Odigbo (2013) affirm that insecurity is the state of being unsafe or insecure or a state of mind characterised by self-doubt and vulnerability. Lastly, American Psychological Association's Dictionary of Psychology defines insecurity as a sense of inadequacy in one or more areas of life; lack of self-confidence; difficulty coping with uncertainty; Abandonment; failure or hardship.

Having explored the views of the various scholars of note regarding the connotations of the word insecurity, they underscore the fact that those affected by insecurity are not only uncertain or unaware of what would happen to them, but they are also vulnerable to the threat and dangers when they occur.

Causes and Negative Effects of Insecurity in Nigerian Society

Despite great potentials that Nigeria as a country has, particularly the abundant natural and intellectual resources, Nigerians are still experiencing higher rate of insecurity which stands as a great barrier posing untold hardship and challenges to its development and growth. Okonkwo and Anigbaju (2015) enumerate some factors causing insecurity in Nigeria which are: unemployment, poverty, differences in religion, corruption, illiteracy, ethnicity, marginalisation, poor parental care, bad governance and poor leadership.

- I. Unemployment and poverty: It is a fact that the menace of unemployment leads to poverty and that the extreme poverty leads to many criminal activities that give birth to insecurity. Aliyu (1998) clarifies poverty as a condition in which people below an expected standard of living with a very meagre income for the immediate need of the people under the family care. Unemployment is also defined as a condition where people are not engaging in any meaningful work or assignment that can provide for their basic needs of life.
- II. Ethnicity and Religious Differences: Both the political and religious leaders in Nigeria occasionally use ethnic or sentiments to achieve their selfish ambitions. Through this means, the

elite group exploits people's mind to stir up mistrust among different groups as well as among the country's major religions causing insecurity. The ideal is that in a multi-ethnic society like Nigeria, the relationship should be cordial, without a reciprocal distrust, fear and a propensity to a violent and confrontation between members of one ethnic or religious group and another (Adagba, 2013).

- III. Corruption has never ceased to be the mother of all evils in Nigeria. It was largely responsible for the government's failure and systematic infrastructural collapse resulting in the large-scale of insecurity in Nigeria which has privatised the important facet of public life. Corruption as a menace is responsible for the massive joblessness of the youths who are the future leaders of Nigeria. Corruption leads the entire youths of Nigeria as a nation to deprivation, poverty, instability, etc. (Adeleke, 2013).
- IV. Boko Haram insurgency is another problem facing the entire nation especially in the northern part of Nigeria because the elite administrators of their governance have jettisoned their creator with greed and corruption, thereby embraced injustice and marginalisation at the expense of justice and equity. All these are the consequences of the shameless looting of public funds which is continuously aggravating the Boko Haram activities in the north (Akpobibibo, 2003).
- V. Multiplicity of Political Parties: Innumerable political parties have caused serious havoc in Nigeria. This is because the ethics of politics remains unknown to the majority of those claiming the ownership of political parties. Instead they were wrapped with misconceptions forgetting that politics is a game of luck and not a do or die affair. Even the incessant rancour among political leaders and political office holders, and rancour between the ruling party and its opposition parties causes

- insecurity of the highest order in the country (Avweromre, 2014).
- VI. Struggle for political power or imposition of candidates for elective posts: Various kinds of impositions such as religious and land disputes, lack of aids and fair treatment or punishment for the victims of trouble-making, corruption, and vandalisation of government properties are another factor fuelling the tension of insecurity in Nigeria (Akonbede, 2013).
 - VII. Porosity of Nigerian borders: Porous borders leading to Nigeria from outside and the neighbouring countries where individual movements are largely untracked have aided the high rate of insecurity in the country. The country therefore witnesses the unchecked inflow of small arms and the light weapons into the country. This has indirectly aided both the militancy and criminality.
 - VIII. Government's failure: Lack of institutional capacity has led to the government's failure in resolving the issue of insecurity in Nigeria. Fukuyama (2004) describes government's failure as a breakdown of institutional infrastructure. This means that the foundations of institutional framework in Nigeria are very shakeable and have provoked an unstable state of governance in Nigeria.
 - IX. Ethno-Religious Crisis: This is a situation in which the dealings or interaction between members of one ethnic or religious group in a multi-religious or multi-ethnic society is characterised by lack of harmonious relationship, cordiality, fear, mutual suspicion, violence and confrontation. In this area, persistent ethnic conflicts and religious clashes exist between the two popular religions (Islam and Christianity).
 - X. Bad governance and poor leadership: The fundamental cause of insecurity since the birth of Nigeria as a nation is traceable to the poor governance and poor leadership role. The sole responsibility of the government is to ensure the provision of basic needs

such as water, electricity, good road network, quality education and the likes. Unfortunately, the aforementioned basic needs are not provided for the people. Therefore, demoralisation, anger etc. may indirectly provide a strong and fertile ground for aggression and general insecurity. Non-availability of these basic amenities in Nigeria is highly embarrassing not because of shortage of funds, but rather due to corruption at the level of leadership structure (Hazen and Horner, 2007).

Origin of Arabic Literature

Al-adab al-Arabiyy (Arabic literature) is coined to denote an expression of emotional feelings in an impressive form. So, the two phrases 'emotional feeling' and 'impressive form' are very important. The first phrase explains the nature of literature while the second one elucidates its subject matter and the theme. Then, the emotional feeling gives rise to expression, and the expression gives birth to the mode in which the feeling is to be made known to others. It is pertinent to note that emotional feeling cannot, on its own, constitute what can be called al-adab unless it is expressed. If the work fails to satisfy the above conditions, it cannot be precisely called Al-adab (literature). For this reason, mathematical calculations and biological and chemical observations are not literature because they are all to senses, and they do not provoke emotional feelings as literature does. Though writing is used to display or describe literature, it, as well, encompasses oral literature as exemplified during the five eras of literature in the early history of Arabs. We can at this juncture conclude that literature is the organisation of words to give pleasure, new experience and transformation of valuable ideas. Research has it that the word al-adab (literature) was not used in the Qur'an neither was it used in the ancient time to mean what we have known it to be today. However, the word al-adab was given variety of meanings such as morality, good conduct, discipline, training, entertainment etc (Hameed,1992) Scholars used different perspectives to interpret or decode the meaning of al-adab. For example, a Nigerian

Arabic poet (Abdullah) uses the word to mean moral when he says:

لا خير في رجل حرّ بلا أدب # نعم
ولو كان منسوباً إلى العرب

“There is no good of a freeman without moral, Even though he belongs to the Arab tribes”

In another dimension, a prophetic hadith employed the word al-adab to mean training when it says:

أدبني ربي فأحسن تأديبي

“My lord has trained me, and made better my training”

Pondering about the uses of the word al-adab in the above two ways as shown in the poetical line and in the prophetic tradition, it has been developed to mean what is known today as Arabic literature.

Arabic Literature as a Cure to the Waves of Insecurity

Public attention could be drawn to the society in particular as well as the entire nation at

large which has been polluted by the so called evil of humanity, and unethical behaviours, thereby causing immoralities ranging from the politics, land disputes, culture, leadership tussle, bad governance and the likes, leading to the insecurity of the highest order. Exploiting the works of Arabic literature serves as food for thought and a tonic for imagination. Acquisition of good moral qualities is equally enhanced. Depriving an individual the chance to acquire the knowledge of Arabic literature is tantamount to the denial of golden opportunities (Adetunji, 2012). For brevity, the poems of Imam al-Shafi' composed on the theme of satisfaction with God's Will and His destiny is our first reference point in this paper. The poet says:

Arabic Text:

وطب نفساً إذا حكم القضاء
فَمَا لِحَوَادِثِ الدُّنْيَا بَقَاءُ
وَشِيَمَتِكَ السَّمَاحَةَ وَالْوَفَاءُ
وَ سِرِّكَ أَنْ يَكُونَ لَهَا غِطَاءُ
يُعْطِيهِ كَمَا قِيلَ السَّخَاءُ
فَإِنَّ شِمَاتَةَ الْأَعْدَاءِ بِلَاءُ
فَمَا فِي النَّارِ لِلظُّمَانِ مَاءُ
وَ لَيْسَ يَزِيدُ فِي الرِّزْقِ الْعَنَاءُ
وَ لَا يُوَسِّسُ عَلَيْكَ وَلَا رَحَاءُ
فَأَنْتَ وَمَالِكَ الدُّنْيَا سَوَاءُ
فَلَا أَرْضُ تَقْبِيهِ وَلَا سَمَاءُ
إِذَا نَزَلَ الْقَحْطَا ضَاقَ الْفَضَاءُ
فَمَا يُغْنِي عَنِ الْمَوْتِ الدَّوَاءُ

Translation:

Let the days do what they want, and be at peace when fate decrees.

دع الأيام تفعل ما تشاء
وَلَا تَجْزَعْ لِحَادِثَةِ اللَّيَالِي
وَ كُنْ رَجُلًا عَلَى الْأَهْوَالِ جَلْدًا
وَ إِنْ كَثُرَتْ عُيُوبُكَ فِي الْبَرَائِيَا
تَسْتَرِّ بِالسَّخَاءِ فَكُلْ عَيْبُ
وَ لَا تَرِ لِلْأَعَادِي قَطُّ دُلًّا
وَ لَا تَرْجُ السَّمَاحَةَ مِنْ بَخِيلٍ
وَ رِزْقُكَ لَيْسَ يُنْقِصُهُ التَّأْنِي
وَ لَا حَزَنٌ يَدُومُ وَ لَا سُرُورٌ
إِذَا مَا كُنْتَ دَا قَلْبٍ قَنُوعِ
وَ مَنْ نَزَلَتْ بِسَاحَتِهِ الْمُنَايَا
وَ أَرْضُ اللَّهِ وَاسِعَةٌ وَ لَكِنْ
دَعِ الْأَيَّامَ تُغْدِرُ كُلَّ حِينِ

And do not be alarmed by the incidents of the nights, for the incidents of this world do not last.

And be a man who can withstand terrors, and
your character is generosity and loyalty.
And if your faults are many in the people, and
you are pleased that they have a cover,

Conceal yourself with generosity, for every
fault, It covers it, as it was said, generosity.
And never show humiliation to enemies, for
the gloating of enemies is a calamity.
And do not expect generosity from the
miserly, for there is no water for the thirsty in
Hell.

And your provision is not diminished by delay,
and toil does not increase provision.
And no sadness lasts nor joy, and no misery or
ease upon you

If you have a contented heart, then you and the
owner of the world are equal.
And he upon whom death descends, there is
no earth or sky to protect him.

And the earth of Allah is vast, but, when the
decree descends, the space narrows.
Leave the days to betray every time, for no
medicine can replace death

Appraisal of the above Poem

The above verses of the poem advise human beings most especially those who do not have positive thinking to the development of their immediate environment, but, instead they make efforts to discourage and jeopardize the development and the advancement in the affairs of their environments or communities. The poet, in the first verse of the poem, admonishes man to shun all forms of adoration of this contemporary period and embrace peace and contentment and to push aside any problem that many pollute their mind negatively. In verse two, the poet warns all humans to face and admit all challenges of life as destined by God, because life challenges are parasite to human existence. In verse three, the poet instills in the man to be courageous and as well display good sense of humanity and loyalty to all and sundry regardless of their status among others. The verses four and five of the poem, say if one is being accused of many irrational behaviors in the midst of people he should endeavour to have a positive change of attitudes, and to

abandon all irrational behaviours are of great advantage to him.

The line six of the poem warns human being to refrain from showing or displaying humiliation, hatred, art of thuggery which may constitute insecurity against our fellow beings this is considered as a grievous calamity that engenders unsafe environment. In line seven, the poet likened the perpetrators of insecurity in the state to the miserly individual from whom any benefit could not be derived as there would be no resting place for the criminals. The line eight of the poem emphasises adequate provision cannot be delayed or deprived as decreed by God, and no labourliness or hard work can multiply it. The philosophy behind this statement is that no one can give himself the needed provision unless it has been destined to happen. Line nine of the poem confirms that fortunes and misfortunes are alien to man in this life, likewise hardship and contentment are not permanent in man's life. Line ten of this poem admonishes human being to be contented. And the poet equates the contented man with those ruling the affairs of the world. In line eleven, the poet describes the sacredness of the death, and that nobody can avert it if really descended on man. In the lines twelve and thirteen, the poet pointed out to the supremacy of death claiming that it has no cure or remedy.

Application

It can be realised from the contents of the above poems that leadership, including other menace, is the problem confronting Nigeria. All our laws regulating our interpersonal relationship are hundred totally perfect, but they are not properly implemented. This poor execution leads to the social insecurity as enumerated in the introductory part of this paper. The researcher holds the view that the problems of some few selfish individuals had snatched the reign of leadership at the detriment of innocent Nigerians. The above verses of the poem pre-empted that the rebirth of the nation is in the hand individuals. As shown in the poem, enmity empowers just one person to destroy a group, but it (the poem) encourages people to be builders rather than destroyers.

Nobody, according to the researcher, understands the reasons for human creation

and our meeting in this journey of life. Though, we may be far from being related by blood, God has united us to live as one big family, because relationship is a silent gift of nature and we should never betray those who love us genuinely. They must not be oppressed, humiliated, harassed, embarrassed, underrated and tampered with the integrity of another fellow being in order to establish true brotherhood among themselves, because the enjoyment of this life is ephemeral. Supporting his stand on the ephemerality of this life, the researcher quotes these two lines of poem:

Arabic Text:

أصل مخلوق تراب ويطود # كل
شئى وإلى الأصل يعود
فلم الفخر لمن قد يهلك # هكذا
إن كان عبداً أو يسود

Translation:

The origin of each creature is soil so, it is confirmed. And everything goes back or returns to its origin.

Why pride in someone who knows that he will return to its origin regardless of whether he is a slave or a master.

Significantly, the implication of the above poem is to embrace this world as mirage or mere an illusion. Therefore, the national or universal brotherhood and goodwill among the people must be extended. In addition harbouring grudges, envy, hatred, keeping malice and enmity must be avoided.

Conclusion

Addressing the negative effects or the challenges of insecurity in Nigeria requires a holistic and multi-dimensional approach. Insecurity produces worries against the targeted goals. In Nigeria for example, insecurity does not spare anybody. This means that every human being faces the challenges of insecurity on daily basis in all areas of life necessitated from incidences like: Fulani herdsmen, Boko Haram insurgences, Armed robbery, pipeline vandalism, Kidnapping, Political/religious crisis, murder, etc.

The menace of above mentioned criminal acts has destabilised the purpose of human creation as enunciated by Almighty Allah in the Glorious Qur'an. Social-political/ and religious affairs in Nigeria are persistently dwindling as another symptom of insecurity

threatening Nigeria. Consequent upon this, the global peace index-GPI (2012) rates Nigeria low regarding its security matters. In essence, adequate security outfit is a progressive wheel of any nation dream, the rapid growth and to be free from insecurity of any form.

Recommendations

As a cankerworm that has deeply affected the Nigerian society, insecurity has hindered both the current and the future of the generations yet unborn. Frantic efforts need to be taken so as to create habitable Nigerian society that may devoid of gross misconducts by all categories of people living in Nigeria so that insecurity may become a forgone issue. Sequel to the researcher's observation, the following recommendations are thereby made:

Flouting a course of study in the curriculum of all institutions of higher learning in Nigeria where the negative implications of insecurity would be exposed to the students, right from their school days. This will lead the students to appreciate and value security. War against insecurity would be easily achievable through the enforcement of fundamental human rights as enshrined in the Nigeria constitution. Also, raising the government's standard of operation to imbibe good governance and to be responsible and accountable for Nigerians as well. The living standards of Nigerian populace should be boosted by establishing more entrepreneurship centres across the nation, particularly in the Northern part of Nigeria part of Nigeria. Another vital step that will help in controlling the menace of insecurity is the creation of job opportunities for the youths so that they may not constitute miscreants.

Therefore, demoralisation and anger may indirectly provide a strong and fertile ground for aggression and general insecurity. All these must be avoided. Non-availability of the basic amenities in Nigeria is highly embarrassing not because of shortage of funds, but due to corruption at all levels of leadership structure (Hazen and Horner, 2007). Nigeria's security apparatus needs to be improved by giving the security agents enough training as well as modern methodologies for using the equipment effectively. Most importantly, literature adds

to morality. According to Akinmulegun (2014), Arabic literature should be an obligatory subject to be read and studied, so that its moral lesson may be acquired and practised. Arabic literature also is employed as being the essential instrument to teaching the students various themes in Arabic literary work. Literature in Arabic creates embodiments of dramatic experience (i.e. Imaginary worlds, ideas, thought and wisdom).

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